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SELF HELP GROUP WOMEN ALSO HAVING STRESS

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Abstract

The empowerment of women by addressing two dimensions: economic empowerment and personal empowerment. One hundred women, aged between 16 and 65 years, participated in self-help groups from two rural Indian villages in North-West India took part in the study. Both quantitative and qualitative data were gathered through self-report surveys and interviews, with the analysis yielding contradictory findings. The quantitative data found that working women reported moderate to high levels on collective efficacy, proactive attitude, self-esteem and self-efficacy with no significant reporting of psychological distress. In contrast, examination of the qualitative data revealed positive appraisals of self-worth, purpose and independence and negative appraisals of pressure, challenge and stress. The implications of these findings and the importance of the present study reveals the SHG stress.

Key words : Women Empowerment, Stress, Self help groups.

Introduction

Stress is an inevitable part of today's fast life. It is a disease of modern times. It affects people regardless of their station in life however stress is more evident and is probably more wide spread in technologically advanced countries. In this age of globalization and liberalization of the economy, competition among organizations has increased. Managers attempt to outperform one another to reach the top. Stress is the order of the day among male and female and is impossible to be entirely without stress. Therefore this study mainly focuses on the causes and issues of stress. Stress of women in self help groups is the focus of this research, Women in self help groups work hard raising funds to live and making things at home, without regular hours, job descriptions, and employee benefits. Instead, they put in long hours of work of shifting clusters of tasks of a schedule set by the needs of the day. It was the industrial revolution and the creation of large manufacturing organizations that created conditions for the emergence of 'work'. a fast moving economy, work is rigid solutions to till elastic concept of change. Surprisingly, these conditions are slowly vanishing. Customized productions are demanding rapid response to changing markets, newly emerging organizational structures, constant need for a work force that could be temporary, part-time, and dynamic with competence to complete specific tasks ill one or more teams. It is another decade; it is possible that jobs will be to a recognizable extent replaced by part time, temporary, work solutions. Organizations may not be able to afford inflexibility of traditional work,

guaranteeing security and satisfaction at work. The new generation organizations may essentially be comprised of temporaries, part timers, consultants, and contract workers, who disband after completing a specified task as it member of a project team, it is likely that organizational participants will work on it or than a team at a time with regular basis at a specified occasion. Emerging technological advancement provides opportunities to work for multiple employers in locations throughout the globe. Flexibility and autonomy are replacing security and predictability ensured by traditional jobs. It is likely that computers, cellular phones, pagers, and the like, will initiate a new and dynamic work environment characterized by multiple employers at the same time in different locations, leading to phenomenal change in the scope for entry of women in the field of entrepreneurship. Employers may tend to opt for providing minimum job description and SHGs Women and SHGs in many parts of the country have achieved success in bringing the women to the main stream of decision making. The SHG in our country has become a source of inspiration For women's welfare formation of SHG is a viable alternative to achieve the objectives of rural development and to get community participation in all rural development programmes. SHG is also a viable organized set up to disburse micro credit to the rural women and encouraging them together into entrepreneurial activities. (Abdul, 2007). To alleviate the poverty and to empower the women, the micro-finance, Self-Help Groups (SHGs) and credit management groups have also started in India.

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Major Problems Faced By the Women Members

Self Help Group is playing a very important role in the process of financial inclusion and women empowerment. Self Help Groups is a small group of poor people 15-20, who voluntarily come together to address their poverty and other social issues. It is formed voluntarily and democratically without any political intervention and affiliation. It can be all women group or all men group or even mixed group. However, over 95% of these SHGs have only women members. The core activity is mobilization of small savings from group members and group lending from accumulated savings as well as bank loans. A great majority of the poor are women due to socio-economic factors, rigidity of gender role, illiteracy, etc. Micro credit has played a catalyst role in organizing these women into Self Help Groups. Empowerment of women has been recognized as a central issue in determining countries like India, women have been discriminated by the society. But now SHGs have provided a forum to express her views, participation in decision making and interaction with each other with the help of micro credit.

Review of Literature

Kumar, (2009) reviewed the scope and limitations of self-help groups in improving women's health and empowerment focusing on the empirical work undertaken in one of the Indian States. They explored the extent to which SHGs could be involved in attaining better health for women and children.

Bharathi & Badiger, (2009) determined the constraints faced by farmwomen self-help-group (SHG) members while working with the NATP project entitled Empowerment of Women in Agriculture, and elicited their suggestions for the further improvement of the project. Lack of formal education was identified as one of the main problems faced by the women. Majority also suggested continuing and expanding the project, increasing the loan amount, and providing information on banking and marketing aspects, among others. The study concluded that it was necessary to improve the literacy of rural women, upgrade and improve their skills, and provide opportunity for them to express their potential abilities.

Rathore and Chabra, (1991) in their paper on 'Promotion of Women in self help groupship-Training Strategies'

state that Indian women find it increasingly difficult to adjust themselves to the dual role that they have to play as traditional housewives and compete with men in the field of business and industry. Working women are often tossed between home and work and experience mental conflicts as they are not able to devote the necessary amount of time and energy to their home and children and find it mostly difficult and sometimes impossible to pursue as a career. A study by Surfi and Surupia showed that the married migrated women in self help groups coming from nuclear families experience greater role stress than the unmarried local women in self help groups coming from joint families.

Srivastava and Chaudhary, (1995) in their work on 'Women in self help groups: Problems Perspective and role expectations from banks, finds out that no single factor but a host of motivating factors act simultaneously on the individual creating dissonance in her, which in turn motivates her to take an action directed towards elimination or reduction of dissonance in the individual. Women faced problems mainly in the areas of marketing of products and approaching the banks for getting loans. Personal problems like time constraint and family stress were also cited. The study concludes that joint family is not an obstacle for developing entrepreneurs. In fact, it is a facilitating factor. The entrepreneurial role enhances familial bonds and increases role satisfaction of women in self help groups as a wife, mother and maker of a 'home'.

Dasgupta (2001) in his paper on informal journey through Self Help Groups observed that micro-financing through informal group approach has effected quite a few benefits viz.: (i) savings mobilized by the poor; (ii) access to the required amount of appropriate credit by the poor; (iii) matching the demand and supply of credit structure and opening new market for FI's; (iv) reduction in transaction cost for both lenders and borrowers; (v) tremendous improvement in recovery; (vi) heralding a new realization of subsidies and corruption less credit, and (vii) remarkable empowerment of poor women. He stresses that SHG's should be considered as one of the best means to counter social and financial citizenship not an end in itself.

Chi-Square Test Value for respondents Age and Self Help Group members Individual (Table -1)

Table - 1

		Individual problem				Health problems	Total	Value	Sig
		Lack of formal education	Excessive tension	Lack of family support	Family responsibilities				
Age	< 20	6	6	6	6	6	30	16.80	.157
	21-30	3	3	3	5	3	17		
	31-40	4	4	6	2	0	18		
	>40	4	6	0	0	11	75		
Total		17	19	15	13				

Chi-square test is used to find out the association between the Age and Self Help Group members Individual problem. From the results it is inferred that there are 19 respondents having excessive tension out of that 6 respondents at the age of less than 20 and 6 of them at the age of more than 40. The chi-square value for this table is 16.80 with respective .157 p-value it is inferred that there is no statistical significant association between Age and Self Help Group members Individual problem.

Chi-Square Test Value for respondents Age and Self Help Group members financial problem.

Table - 2

		Financial problem				Fixed capital problem	Total	Value	Sig.
		Shortage of capital	Lack of security	High interest	Insufficient loan				
Age	< 20	0	6	18	3	3	30	26.80	.008
	21-30	3	11	3	0	0	17		
	31-40	2	6	4	2	4	18		
	>40	2	4	4	0	0	10		
Total		7	27	29	5	7	75		

Chi-square test is used to find out the association between the Age and Self Help Group members financial problem. From the results it is inferred that there are 29 respondents having financial problem with high interest out of that 20 respondents at the age of less than 20. The chi-square value for this table is 26.80 with respective .008 p-value it is inferred that there is statistical significant association between Age and Self Help Group members financial problem.

Chi-Square Test Value for respondent's type family type and Self Help Group members' socio family problem.

Table - 3

		Socio family problem				Lack of colleagues support	Total	Value	Sig.
		Lack of social support	Male domination	Lack of family support	Traditional barriers				
Type of family	Joint	10	5	8	10	6	39	10.90	.028
	Nuclear	3	14	5	5	9	36		
Total		13	19	13	15	15	75		

Chi-square test is used to find out the association between the family type and Self Help Group socio family problem. From the results it is inferred that there are 19 respondents having socio family problem with male domination society out of that 14 respondents are from Nuclear family. The chi-square value for this table is 10.90 with respective .028 p-value it is inferred that there is statistical significant association between family type and Self Help Group members socio family problem.

Chi-Square Test Value for respondents education and Self Help Group members financial problem.

Table - 4

		Financial Problem					Total	Value	Sig.
		Shortage of capital	Lack of security	High interest	Insufficient loan	Fixed capital problem			
Education	Illiterate	0	5	3	0	0	8	33.44	.006
	Up to 5th std	2	11	3	3	0	19		
	5th to 10th std	3	6	12	0	3	24		
	Higher secondary	2	0	5	2	4	13		
	Degree	0	5	6	0	0	11		
Total		7	27	29	5	7	75		

Chi-square test is used to find out the association between education and Self Help Group members financial problem. From the results it is inferred that there are 29 respondents having financial problem with high interest out of that 12 respondents have 5th standard to 10th standard education. The chi-square value for this table is 33.44 with respective .006 with p-value it is inferred that there is statistical significant association between education and Self Help Group members financial problem.

Chi-Square Test Value for respondent's marital status and Self Help Group members' financial problem

Table - 5

		Financial problem					Total	Value	Sig.
		Shortage of capital	Lack of security	High interest	Insufficient loan	Fixed capital problem			
Marital status	Married	0	8	0	0	0	8	53.78	.000
	Un-married	0	6	3	2	2	13		
	Widows	5	5	7	0	0	17		
	Divorcee	0	6	19	3	2	30		
	Separated	2	2	0	0	3	7		
Total		7	27	29	5	7	75		

Chi-square test is used to find out the association between the marital status and Self Help Group members financial problem. From the results it is inferred that there are 19 divorcee respondents having financial problem with high interest. The chi-square value for this table is 53.78 with respective .000 p-value it is inferred that there is statistical significant association between respondents marital status and Self Help Group members financial problem.

Chi-Square Test Value for respondent's monthly family income and Self Help Group members' financial problem

Table - 6

		Financial problem					Total	Value	Sig.
		Shortage of capital	Lack of security	High interest	Insufficient loan	Fixed capital problem			
Family income	<10000	3	3	3	0	3	12	48.32	.000
	10001-20000	0	14	6	3	0	23		
	20001-30000	2	0	15	0	2	19		
	30001-40000	2	2	3	2	0	9		
	>40000	0	8	2	0	2	12		
Total		7	27	29	5	7	75		

Chi-square test is used to find out the association between monthly family income and Self Help Group members' financial problem. From the results it is inferred that there are 29 respondents having financial problem with high interest out of them 15 respondents from 20001-30000 monthly family income. The chi-square value for this table is 48.32 with respective .000 p-value it is inferred that there is statistical significant association between respondents' monthly family income and Self Help Group members' financial problem.

Analysis of variance results for Educational Qualification of the respondents and social Support

Table - 7

	Education	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig.
Individual problem	Illiterate	8	2.87	1.24	3.99	.00
	Up to 5th std	19	3.00	1.37		
	5th to 10th std	24	3.12	1.36		
	Higher secondary	13	2.84	1.40		
	Degree	11	1.36	.50		
	Total	75	2.76	1.37		
Financial problem	Illiterate	8	2.37	.51	2.86	.03
	Up to 5th std	19	2.36	.89		
	5th to 10th std	24	2.75	1.11		
	Higher secondary	13	3.46	1.39		
	Degree	11	2.54	.522		
	Total	75	2.70	1.04		
Marketing problem	Illiterate	8	3.37	1.40	1.66	.19
	Up to 5th std	19	3.10	1.10		

	5th to 10th std	24	2.87	1.03		
	Higher secondary	13	2.15	1.34		
	Degree	11	2.90	1.44		
	Total	75	2.86	1.23		
Socio family problem	Illiterate	8	3.12	1.80	2.10	.09
	Up to 5th std	19	3.52	.96		
	5th to 10th std	24	3.16	1.60		
	Higher secondary	13	2.46	1.26		
	Degree	11	2.27	1.10		
	Total	75	3.00	1.40		
Product related problem	Illiterate	8	2.75	1.38	2.57	.05
	Up to 5th std	19	3.21	1.35		
	5th to 10th std	24	2.08	1.21		
	Higher secondary	13	2.84	1.21		
	Degree	11	3.09	1.04		
	Total	75	2.72	1.30		

Individual problem

The obtained 'F' value is 3.99 and it is significant at 1% level. The value indicates that there is no significant influence of education on individual problem.

Further, the mean indicates that the studied up to 10th standard have scored higher mean value of 3.12 and the lowest mean value was scored by the degree holder employees (1.36). This shows that the graduate employees having less individual problems than the respondents finished their education up to 10th standard.

Financial problem

The obtained 'F' value is 2.66 and it is not significant at 1% level. The value indicates that there is no significant influence of education on financial problem.

Further, the mean indicates that the studied up to higher secondary scored higher mean value of 3.46 and the lowest mean value was scored by the respondent's finished their education up to 10th standard (2.36). This shows that the higher secondary educated employees having more financial problems than the respondents finished their education up to 5th standard.

Marketing problem

The obtained 'F' value is 1.66 and it is not significant at 1% level. The value indicates that there is no significant influence of education on marketing problem.

Further, the mean indicates that the illiterate employees having higher mean value of 1.66 and the lowest mean value was scored by the respondent's finished their education up to higher secondary (2.15). This shows that the higher secondary educated employees having less marketing problems than the illiterate respondents.

Socio family problem

The obtained 'F' value is 2.10 and it is not significant at 1% level. The value indicates that there is no significant influence of education on socio family problem

Further, the mean indicates that the respondents studied up 5th standard scored higher mean value of 3.52 and the lowest mean value was scored by the respondents finished their degree (2.27). This shows that the respondents

finished their education up to 5th standard having more social family problems than the respondents finished their degree.

Product related problem

The obtained 'F' value is 2.57 and it is not significant at 1% level. The value indicates that there is no significant influence of education on product related problem.

Further, the mean indicates that the respondents studied up to 5th standard scored higher mean value of 3.21 and the lowest mean value was scored by the respondent's finished their education between 5th and 10th standard (2.08). This shows that the respondents finished their education up to 5th standard having more product related problems than the respondents finished their education between 5th and 10th standard.

Findings

- There is no statistical significant association between Age and Self Help Group member's Individual problem.
- Statistical significant association between Age and Self Help Group member's financial problem.
- There is no statistical significant association between family type and Self Help Group member's financial problem.
- There is statistical significant association between family type and Self Help Group member's socio family problem.
- There is statistical significant association between education and Self Help Group member's financial problem.
- There is statistical significant association between education and Self Help Group member's family problem.
- There is statistical significant association between respondent's marital status and Self Help Group members financial problem.
- There is statistical significant association between respondents monthly family income and Self Help Group members financial problem
- The employees are getting less salary having marketing problem than the employees are getting more salary.
- The graduate employees having less individual problems than the respondent's finished their education up to 10th standard.
- This shows that the higher secondary educated employees having more financial problems than the respondent's finished their education up to 5th standard.

- The higher secondary educated employees having less marketing problems than the illiterate respondents
- The respondents finished their education up to 5th standard having more social family problems than the respondents finished their degree
- The respondents finished their education up to 5th standard having more product related problems than the respondents finished their education between 5th and 10th standard.

Suggestion and Conclusion

From the study it was found that the self help group member women having more stress due to financial problem especially with high interest and problems leads to stress because of low education level. The following recommendations will be given to empowering women in SHGs and stress must be eliminated.

- That All SHG women members should be given back knowledge about SHGs and it's importance
- Problems faced by SHG members should be regularly attended to and given solutions
- Adequate insurance coverage should be provided to the business units promoted by SHG against the financial losses to safeguard the interest of the entrepreneurs
- Training programmes relating to management of finances, maintaining accounts, production and marketing Activities etc. should be given
- There should be a continuous flow of funds to Self Help Groups
- Loan amount should be increased
- Follow up should be increased and unity should be improved
- Information on banking and marketing aspects should be given.
- Adequate knowledge about the importance of education should be promoted.
- Family members support will be given through volunteers in the society.

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